

**INTERACTIVE EDUCATIONAL METHODS USED IN TEACHING THE
ETHICAL VIEWS OF SADI SHERAZI**

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Abstract: This article discusses the interactive educational methods used in teaching the moral views of Saadi Shirazi.

Keywords: moral views, universal values, the structure of self-awareness, teacher and student etiquette, moral principles, and the idea of goodness.

It calls for a systematic analysis of views on the issues of perfect human education, beautiful human qualities, the harmony of intelligence and love, peace, harmony, calmness, harmony in social existence in the works of Saadi Shirazi, and the implementation of scientific research in this direction. As a result of the reforms in the scientific, spiritual, and cultural spheres carried out in our country, great attention is being paid to the study of the scientific and spiritual heritage of our world-famous scholars and thinkers, as well as their socio-philosophical ideas. "The unique and unique scientific and spiritual heritage of our great ancestors should become a living program in constant motion for us. This immortal heritage should always be with us and always give us strength and inspiration." From this point of view, the implementation of socio-philosophical research, which is considered an integral part of the spiritual heritage of our ancestors, is an important topic of scientific research.

Saadi's works have been popular among the Uzbek people since ancient times. The works of "Boston" and "Gulistan" have been taught as main textbooks in madrasahs. Our classic poets learned and were influenced by this great artist of words. Alisher Navoi's "Mahbub ul-Qulub", Khoja's "Gulzor", and Abdulla Avlani's "Turkish Gulistan" or "Morality" were created directly under the influence of Saadi's Gulistan. There are 22 verses to Saadi's ghazals in "Devoni Foniy", and 4 ghazals in his style. For example, in a preface written by Navoiyni to Saadi's ghazal, we read:

Фоний, ба раҳи Саъдий агар зад қадаме чанд,
Бо ў суханаш бин, ки чу шири шакар афтод.

Content: "Because Fany took a few steps on the path of Saadi, his words became sweet like milk and sugar."

Of course, as a representative of Sufi literature, Sadi also wrote Sufi poems (in the second chapter of "Gulistan" he tells the story of his childhood with his father in a meeting of Sufis). But in them too, in Navoi's words, real and figurative love was skillfully mixed up. According to "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat" Tazkir, Sa'di Shirazy was visited by Khizr. Amir Khusrav Dehlavi, who was going through the stages of Riyazat under the guidance of the famous Piri Nizamuddin Auliya, saw Khizr alaihissalam in a dream one night and asked him to put a blessed kiss on his mouth. But Khizr said: "This state was given to Saadi before you!"

The best of the Uzbek translations of the works of the great Persian-Tajik poet was selected for this collection, starting with the work of Saadiy Shirozi, who is being brought to the attention of fans of Eastern classical art. It is known that the work "Guliston", which is written in folk Uelub mixed with prose and poetry, has gained great fame due to its wealth of narration, narration, and wisdom, and has been translated into Uzbek several times. This work was translated for the first time in 1390-1391 in Egypt by one of the major figures of Uzbek literature of the XIV century, Saifi Saroyi, under the name "Guliston bit-turkiy".

Sayfi Saraoi, at the invitation of her friends and colleagues, translated "Gulistan" into the dialect of the Uzbek language. He has preserved the original of the work, but at the same time, he has deviated from the original. This is also related to the period factor: in the Middle Ages, translation was approached somewhat freely - the translator could shorten, change, or even add to the work. Saifi Saraoi also omitted some passages from "Gulistan" during the translation process, creatively reworked some poems, included some poems of his own and contemporary poets, and left some of them alone without translating them. Nevertheless, the translation was successful and over the centuries played an important role in introducing the Turkic peoples to the work of Saadi and promoting the spiritual and moral views of the wise poet.

In the XIX century, "Gulistan" was translated into Uzbek for the second time by the great poet and skilled translator Muhammadrizo Ogahi, on the order of Khiva Khan Muhammad Rahimkhan II - Feruz. Even though he translated the work somewhat abbreviated, for example, leaving 25 out of 187 stories, turning 522 stanzas out of 1,000 poetic fragments into verse, and not translating some Arabic texts into Uzbek, "Ogahi Saadiy conveys the artistic freshness and spirit of Shirozi's stories to the reader. Sa'di's prayers, his prose composed in concise but rather aphoristic sentences, verses and rubaiy, serohong, sonorous expressions are reflected in Uzbek sophistication in Ogahi's translation" (N.Komilov).

The third translation of "Guliston" was written by the son of Mulla Murodhoja Salihhoja, a teacher and poet from Tashkent, and it was called "Shavqi Gulistan". "Taking into account the needs of madrasa students, Murodhoja commented on the difficult words and phrases of the work and added the Persian original and published it in the Ghulomiya printing house" (1909). However, due to the superiority of the principle of literal translation and the lack of a high artistic level, this translation did not gain much fame.

In 1968, the fourth translation of Gulistan was published. The poems in the work were translated into Uzbek by Gafur Ghulam and Shoislam Shomuhamedov, and the prose part by Rustam Komilov. This was an important step in introducing "Gulistan" to the modern reader. Although "Bo'ston" was first translated by Chustiy and then by Sh. Shomuhamedov, both of these translations are incomplete. The work has been shortened and adapted to the times. It was translated into Uzbek without the religious-mystical parts. But beautiful and meaningful stories and deep wisdom at the level of folk proverbs give a complete picture of the work and attract any reader.

Of course, this graduation thesis on the topic "Ethical views of Saadi Shirazy" is chosen by the author from the point of view of the scientific study of the work and heritage of world literature leader Saadi Shirazy. After all, each era has its demand and its readers for the masterpieces of artists like Saadi Shirazi. In this respect, Saadi Shirazi makes new translations and publications necessary for his moral views.

Armed with the most advanced and modern technologies of the world, with a high level of professional skills, capable of withstanding strong competition, and able to ensure modern development by international requirements, the training of brave, independent, creative-thinking, competent, knowledgeable specialists, as well as well-rounded personnel with personal human qualities, is the goal of higher education.

Today, such concepts as pedagogical technologies, and active and interactive teaching methods are widely used in the field of education. The word technology entered pedagogy from the field of production. As we know, any technology is focused on the final result, it plans and implements it step by step. The most important thing is that the final result is guaranteed in any technology.

"Pedagogical technology" means an educational and educational process that is designed in advance and guarantees the final result.

Today, along with traditional educational technologies, unconventional (non-standard, advanced, modern, new, innovative) technologies are being used in the educational process.

Such technologies include:

Problem-based education is an education aimed at forming skills and competencies in students such as creative research, conducting small research, putting forward certain hypotheses, substantiating results, and coming to certain conclusions. Analyzing and thinking about the problems that have arisen is one of the important requirements for the development of independent mental activity in students. This kind of thinking causes the student to realize that he/she has not understood the point and to pay serious attention to the meaning of the statement.

Computer education is an education organized based on computer technology, telecommunication tools, and software-methodical support as a model of the pedagogue's activity of collecting and transmitting information in the management of cognitive activities of students, which includes reading, independent education, and self-control.

Computer education technologies - forms, methods, and tools of education organized based on computer equipment, telecommunication tools, and software-methodical support as a model of the pedagogue's activity of collecting and transmitting information in the management of learning activities of learners, which includes learning, independent education and self-control set. Among these types of technologies, technologies that serve to form the skills for working with information, develop intellectual abilities, create conditions for independent education, and develop and evaluate research activities are widespread.

Module education is a specific form of organization of the educational process, according to which the educational material is mastered based on certain stages and steps based on logically completed units - modules. The technology of modular training is an increasingly popular type of education - modular training or modular training.

Distance education is directed to the use of educational resources based on traditional and innovative forms, methods, and tools in the provision of educational services, distribution, and delivery of educational products from a certain point using information and communication tools (video, audio, computer, multimedia, radio, television, etc.). education. Distance education technologies are a set of forms, methods, and tools aimed at ensuring the implementation of education based on the specified content. These technologies include the technologies of providing educational information, transmitting educational information, and storing and processing educational information.

Collaborative education is an education that represents the joint acquisition of knowledge by students in a team, small group, or pair, mutual development, the cooperative organization of the "teacher-student(s)" relationship, and its main idea is to complete educational tasks in a team,

small group or pair together, in cooperation. perform

Several passive, active, interactive, and training are widely used in the implementation of this training technology.

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